

ARTISTIC ELEMENT IN THE JOURNALISM OF JACK LONDON

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Abstract. This article talks about fiction, journalism, the famous works of Jack London's life and work, and some of the world's favorite narrative novels.

Key words: fiction, journalism, Jack London.

ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫЙ ЭЛЕМЕНТ В ЖУРНАЛИСТИКЕ ДЖЕКА ЛОНДОНА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о художественной литературе, журналистике, известных произведениях из жизни и творчества Джека Лондона, а также о некоторых самых популярных в мире повествовательных романах.

Ключевые слова: художественная литература, журналистика, Джек Лондон.

The term literary journalism is sometimes used interchangeably, not creatively; However, it is often seen as a form of creativity.

Literary journalists in the US today include John McPhee, Jane Kramer, Mark Singer and Richard Rhodes. Some literary journalists of the past century include Stephen Crane, Jack London, George Orwell, and Tom Wolfe. This article provides an analytical understanding of the works of Jack London, the problems in society and its impact on people [1]. Jack London's novel "Martin Eden" talks about the inner world of man, hard work and struggle for life. These qualities are embodied in the character of Martin in the novel [2]. The purpose of the article is to determine the uniqueness of the artistic world in Jack London's work. In 1900-1910, the writer translated his works in connection with the specific features of the interpretation of "man-nature-civilization" problems [3].

John Griffith Chaney, Jack London, was born on January 12, 1876. He is an American writer who has written fiction and non-fiction books, short stories, poems, plays and essays. Jack London was born in San Francisco, California. His mother, Flora Wellman, was living with William Chaney, a lawyer and astrologer, and became pregnant with Jack. Jack London had socialist views. These ideas are reflected in his writing, speeches and other activities. He was a member of the Socialist Workers Party and the Socialist Party of America. He was a socialist candidate who ran for mayor of Oakland in 1901 and 1905, but he did not receive the necessary votes to get elected. In 1906, he gave speeches on a number of socialist topics around the country. Among his best-known works are Call of the Wild and White Tooth, both Klondike Gold Rush, as well as the short stories To Build a Fire, A Northern Odyssey, and Love of Life. He also wrote about the South Pacific "Pearls of Parlay" and "Heathen". The term literary journalism is sometimes used interchangeably, not creatively; However, it is often seen as a form of creativity. Jack London wrote about romanticism and the difficulties of ordinary life in his works. London was one of the first writers to gain worldwide fame and fortune by writing a single work. Jack London published his first two novels, The Dazzler's Cruise and Snow Maiden, in 1902. A year later, at the age of 27, he achieved commercial success with his best-known novel, The Challenge. Savage is a short adventure novel set in the 1890s during the Klondike Gold Rush, set during London's year in the Yukon and centered around a Saint Bernard-Scotch shepherd named Buck. The book remains in print today. London was part of the radical literary group The Crowd in San Francisco and a

passionate advocate of trade unionism, workers' rights, socialism, and eugenics. He has written several works on similar themes, such as the dystopian novel *The Iron Heel*, his fiction expose *The Abyss*, *Class War* and *Before Adam*. Jack London's works are famous all over the world, his works reflect the colorfulness of life, glorification of love, and the struggle of people with wild nature. Jack London's work is diverse - protest against the bourgeois system, socialist ideas, individualism, and even themes of peace and stability in the last years of his work can be seen in his works. London's first creative work and essay "Typhoon off the coast of Japan" was awarded and presented on November 12, 1893. After returning from Alaska, he seriously entered the field of literature and in 1899 published his Northern stories. In 1890, his first book "The Son of the Wolf" was published. In these bright and original works, Jack London shows his opposition to social injustice, inequality and inferiority of people, the author contrasts these qualities with the cold climate of the north and the strong character of people who are left behind by civilization. London often portrays uncivilized Indians and Pacific peoples as innocent, strong and courageous people. The heroes of London are, first of all, ordinary hardworking people who try to face difficulties and overcome them. For example, ordinary sailor Martin Eden, amateur boxer Felipe Rivera, university professor Freddie Drummond - all of them are people who respect work and pay attention to the events around them.

Jack London is the most widely read American writer in the world. According to UNESCO, in 2004 his works were published in 31 countries of the world. He is one of the pioneers of American literature, and he is considered a writer who started a unique, progressive tradition. Jack London was the first American writer who gained popularity not only in the United States of America, but throughout the world in the 20th century. In American literature, Jack London continues the humanist movement of Walt Whitman.

Although modernist trends appeared after World War II, we can still see the tradition of trust in people in the works of American literature representatives. Most of the writer's story collections, a number of short stories and novels were written on the northern. *Snow Maiden* (1902), *Spark of Life* (1907), *Northern Odyssey* (1910), *Faith in Man* (1914), *Like Ancient Sailors* (1917), *Scarred Man* (1900), *Gold gorge* (1905) and others. author of adventure works. "In a Far Country" (1899), "Female Courage" (1900), "Lighting a Bonfire" (1910), In his works "The Story of Winter" (1904), he described the unique life of the hardworking Indians who were in harmony with nature. The works "Wild Power" (1905), "White Fang" (1906) are about the animal world. The novels "The Sea Wolf" (1904), "Martin Eden" (1909), "Three Hearts" (1920) are famous. The influence of the philosophical teachings of G. Spencer and F. Nietzsche can be felt in London's work. In the novel-biography "Martin Eden", the main character reflected his "passion for life" even when he was full of money. In his novel written under the influence of individualism, the western theory of "perfect man", i.e. "superman" is put forward.

After his trip to England in 1903, he published a collection of essays called "People of the Bottom". In this book, the writer describes the poor life of London workers. The writer strongly criticizes the bourgeois society in the novel "Iron Heel" (1907), another of his best novels "Martin Eden" (1909).

London often portrays uncivilized Indians and Pacific peoples as innocent, strong and courageous people. London shows them as incomparable romantics and praises their natural enthusiasm, courage and readiness to fight for life ("Northern Odyssey", "The Legend of Kische",

"White Silence", etc.). London "White silence" - incomparably glorifies those who overcome the snow and can withstand the harsh weather. *Martin Eden* is a book about a victim of love who found his life path through the great power and human tenacity of his accidental love, which eventually led him to maturity, but which guaranteed his inevitable doom. Despite this, he is a simple ship's captain who can show what a person can and can achieve in life. The high peak of maturity is due to his unattainable original love and the ability to love the beauty that lies dormant in the corner of his heart.

Jack London had socialist views. These views were evident in his writing, speeches and other activities. He was a member of the Socialist Labor Party and the Socialist Party of America. He was the Socialist candidate for mayor of Auckland in 1901 and 1905, but he did not receive the necessary votes to be elected. In 1906, he gave several lectures on socialist topics around the country and also published several essays sharing his socialist views.

Although books are more common today than movies, this was not the case in Jack London's day. He was one of the first writers to work on film when his novel *The Wolf-Wolf* was made into the first full-length American film.

London was also a pioneer in the science fiction genre. To do this, he wrote about apocalyptic catastrophes, future wars and scientific dystopias before the usual. Later science fiction writers, such as George Orwell, cited London books, including *Adam* and *The Iron Heel*, as influences on their work.

Jack London died on November 22, 1916 at the age of 40 at his home in California. About his death, some people claimed that he committed suicide. However, he suffered from many health problems later in life and the official cause of death was listed as kidney disease.

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